

**Combating gender stereotypes by
highlighting women's contribution to the
history of societies**

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Martinique

Martinique is a French territorial collectivity located in the Antilles (Caribbean region), between the English-speaking islands of Dominica and Saint Lucia. From the 17th to the 19th century, it was the site of the enslavement of West Africans and their descendants. The abolition of slavery in Martinique occurred on May 22, 1848, following the French government's decision to abolish slavery in all French colonies. After emancipation, former slaves in Martinique faced various challenges as they sought to build new lives and improve their socio-economic conditions. That's why the question of gender equality and gender representation was not the principal concern for the people of Martinique, comparing to Metropolitan France where feminist mobilization was already well underway in 1848. So, it's only recently that these issues have taken an important place in Martinique.

Today, it's observed that in Martinique, many gender inequalities persist. The island's history but also the structural constraints can have significant effects on the status, opportunities, and rights of women, contributing to gender inequality. These constraints refer to the social norms, policies, laws, and institutionalized practices that perpetuate gender inequalities.

One of the first effects of these constraints is an unequal division of labor between men and women that persists in Martinique. During the colonial period, women in Martinique were largely excluded from positions of power and authority. The dominant patriarchal system limited their participation in public life and confined them to domestic and reproductive roles.

Today, although women are generally more highly educated than men, they are more often unemployed with the same level of qualifications. They are also certain sectors or industries dominated by one gender. Women are often concentrated in lower-paying and less valued sectors, while men dominate higher-paying positions and leadership within companies (managers, CEOs, senior executives, business owners). This occupational segregation contributes to limited career advancement opportunities but also income disparities. In fact, for the same job, women in Martinique earn more than 2000 euros less a year than men¹. This gender wage gap is also reinforced by other economic disparities between women and men. Women in Martinique may face obstacles in accessing economic resources such as credit, land ownership, or entrepreneurship opportunities and hinder women's economic independence and autonomy.

¹ According to figures published by INSEE, in 2022, women's net annual salary was 25,201 euros, compared with 27,877 euros for men.

Structural constraints can also impede women's political participation and representation. In Martinique, women are underrepresented in political spheres, both at the local and national levels, due to obstacles such as sexist biases, discriminatory practices, and limited access to political networks and resources. And even if the representation of women among elected representatives is improving, few hold positions of responsibility. Consequently, women are often marginalized in political decision-making, limiting their ability to influence policies and advocate for gender equality issues.

Today, only five women are mayors and nine are first deputies in Martinique's thirty-four communes. None presides over the three agglomeration communities, and only one is first vice-president². However, the last years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of women's participation in decision-making processes. Efforts have been made to increase women's representation in politics and ensure that their voices are heard in policymaking and governance.

These constraints can also contribute to higher rates of gender-based violence against women. Norms and attitudes that perpetuate gender inequalities can normalize and tolerate certain forms of violence against women and reinforce abusive behaviors. This is a significant issue in Martinique, where physical and psychological violence against women is very prevalent.

All the structural constraints are reinforced by cultural norms and stereotypes deeply ingrained in society (it's very visible in Martinique) that perpetuate traditional gender roles and expectations. This can exert social pressures on women to conform to certain standards of beauty, behavior, and social roles, restricting their autonomy and freedom of choice in various areas of life, including education, employment, and decision-making.

By addressing these structural constraints and promoting gender equality, Martinique can work towards creating a more inclusive and equitable society for all.

2. Gender Representation in history

Gender representation in Martinique's history has often been biased and unequal, with women's contributions and experiences marginalized or neglected. The historical narrative has mainly focused on the achievements and perspectives of men, while women's voices and roles have been largely ignored. This is the case in France, but even more in Martinique.

² Jean-Marc Party, Femmes en politique en Martinique : des progrès restent à accomplir, in Martinique la 1^{ère} France Télévision, 8 march 2023. <https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/martinique/femmes-en-politique-en-martinique-des-progres-restent-a-accomplir-1373046.html>

In recent years, efforts have been made to discover and highlight the important contributions of women in shaping the history of Martinique. A more balanced gender representation in crucial areas such as history is essential because the underrepresentation of women in history can lead to a biased and incomplete view of the past, primarily highlighting male achievements and perpetuating gender inequalities in society. A fair representation of both women and men in history allows for the recognition of the contributions and achievements of Martinican women who have played significant roles in the development of society, culture, and social movements.

To achieve this goal, it is crucial to promote and support inclusive historical research that highlights the role of women in various aspects of Martinican society. This also includes disseminating this knowledge through education, media, publications, and other means so that current and future generations can have a better understanding of history in all its diversity and enrichment through women's contributions.

By including female perspectives in the history of Martinique, a better understanding of the impact of women can be achieved. It also promotes the identification of role models for future generations, demonstrating that women have always been active and influential in shaping the region's history.

3. Women's footprint in Martinique

In France, women's footprints are not often highlighted compared to men's, but in Martinique, the situation is worse. The society is very misogynistic and the relations between women and men in the society are unequal, with a dominance of the male gender. This is visible in history curricula, narratives, but also through the number of streets, statues and monuments dedicated to women. In Fort-de-France, for example, the capital of Martinique, there are only 14 streets named after women which shows the low presence of women on the island. A woman's street was even renamed after a man after the street was relocated.

Although we don't talk about it much, many Martinican women have played crucial roles in various fields, leaving a positive impact and imprint in the history. Women in Martinique have been leaders, activists, educators, artists, entrepreneurs, among many other roles.

Historically, women have been at the forefront of social movements, fighting for civil rights, labor rights, and gender equality. They have been active participants in shaping the political landscape and advocating for important societal changes.

In the fields of arts and culture, women in Martinique have been influential in literature, music, dance, and visual arts, enriching the island's cultural heritage and promoting its

unique identity. Male writers such as Aimé Césaire and Édouard Glissant for example have achieved international recognition, but the contributions of women authors and artists have often been underrepresented.

Additionally, women have been pivotal in the economic development of Martinique through entrepreneurship and leadership in various industries.

It is essential to recognize and celebrate the significant contributions of Martinican women and to continue promoting gender equality, empowering women, and ensuring that their voices are heard and valued in all aspects of society. By acknowledging and appreciating their footprint, we can build a more inclusive and equitable future for Martinique.

Here are some women who have left their mark in history but have not been highlighted:

3.1. Jane Léro (1916-1961)

Jane Léro was a Martinican activist and feminist. She is known for her advocacy for women's rights and the promotion of gender equality in Martinique. She founded *l'Union des Femmes de la Martinique* (UFM), the first feminist organization.

She is a significant figure in the social and political movements in Martinique during the 1940s and 1950s. Jane Léro also participated in local feminist movements and was a vocal advocate against gender inequalities and social injustices. She played an important role in raising awareness about the specific issues faced by Martinican women at that time and her work contributed to paving the way for future advancements in the fight for gender equality in the society.

3.2. Lumina Sophie (1848-1879)

Lumina Sophie also called Surprise was a Martinican activist and poet. She was an advocate for women's rights, education, and workers' rights. Surprise used her poetry to address social and political issues, and she was an influential figure in the cultural and political spheres of Martinique. She spoke out against the segregation and racism that persisted in Martinique after the abolition of slavery and took part in the southern insurrection of September 1870. She was arrested a few days later. After two trials, she was sentenced to forced labour for life. After giving birth in prison, she was transferred to the penal colony of Guyana where she died on December 15th, 1879.

3.3. Suzanne Roussi-Césaire (1915-1966)

Suzanne Roussi-Césaire, born in Martinique, was a writer, poet, anti-colonial and feminist activist and cultural figure. She co-founded the literary journal "Tropiques"

(1941-1945) with her husband Aimé Césaire, providing a platform for Caribbean intellectuals and artists. Like many women in history, Suzanne Césaire has been overshadowed by the fame of her husband. Her ideas have not only been poorly read and rarely analyzed but have also been sometimes wrongly attributed. For example, in the article she published in 1948 in "Présence africaine" about the novel "Je suis martiniquaise", by Mayotte Capécia, Jenny Alpha wrongly attributes Suzanne Césaire's aesthetic decree "La poésie martiniquaise sera cannibal ou ne sera pas" to her husband³. Furthermore, often racialized and exoticized, Suzanne Césaire has essentially been associated with the status of Aimé Césaire's wife. However, Suzanne Césaire is the author of a work that has been overlooked for too long but is essential to the literary history of the Caribbean.

3.4. The Nardal sisters

The Nardal sisters were significant figures in the intellectual and cultural movement of Négritude in Martinique and France. They played a key role in recognizing and valorizing black culture and identity, as well as fighting against racism and social injustices. Their literary works, editorial activities, and political engagement had a significant influence on raising awareness of the history and contributions of black people in the francophone world. They paved the way for many other writers and intellectuals who continued to explore and celebrate the diversity and richness of black culture.

Paulette Nardal (1896-1985) was a writer, poet, and feminist. She arrived in Paris in 1920 and enrolled at the Sorbonne University to study English. She became the first black woman to study at this French institution. She co-founded the literary journal "La Revue du Monde Noir" in Paris in the 1920s, which served as a platform for black intellectuals and inspired Afro-feminism and, more broadly, intersectional feminism. Paulette Nardal wrote essays and articles that contributed to the emergence of Négritude as a literary and political movement. But like many women, her ideas and contributions have been overshadowed or attributed to men. In a letter to biographer Léopold Sédar Senghor, Paulette wrote: "*Césaire and Senghor took up the ideas we brandished and expressed them with much more sparkle - we were only women! We paved the way for men*"⁴.

Jeanne Nardal (1902-1993) was also a major figure of the Négritude movement. She contributed to the creation of the journal *Légitime Défense* in Paris in the 1930s, which

³ Philippe Triay. *Encore peu connue, l'œuvre de Suzanne Césaire décryptée par l'universitaire Anny-Dominique Curtius*, in Martinique la 1^{ère} France Télévision, 22 January 2021, <https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/encore-peu-con nue-l-uvre-de-suzanne-cesaire-decryptee-par-l-universitaire-anny-dominique-curtius-915133.html>

⁴ Bertin-Elisabet, C., "Les Nardal : Textes, co-textes, contextes". *Fédérer Langues, Altérités, Marginalités, Médias, Éthique*, (1), 2021, <https://doi.org/10.25965/flamme.89>

promoted black culture and ideas. Jeanne Nardal used her writing to denounce racism and social inequalities while encouraging pride and appreciation of African culture.

Andrée Nardal (1910-1935) was also involved in the Négritude movement but is primarily known for her role as a teacher and educator in Martinique. She founded a private school that played a significant role in spreading Négritude ideas and promoting education among young Martinicans.

3.5. Manon Tardon (1913-1989)

Manon Tardon is a prominent figure of the French Resistance and the Free France movement. During the Second World War, she joined the army and attends the General Delattre de Tassigny School for Officers. She became a specialist in the Women's Division of the Army (Arme Féminine de l'Armée de Terre), first at the rank of aspirant, and later promoted to an officer and lieutenant. She actively participates in various resistance networks of Free France and was decorated with the "Croix de Guerre of Free France"⁵.

3.6. Luce Le Maistre (1912-2000)

Luce Lemaistre was Martinique's first female mayor. She was elected in 1949 in the new commune of Morne-Vert. Although her term was not long (2 years), at that time it was something important as women had just obtained the right to vote (in 1944). Indeed, the women's right to vote took a long time to be established. There have been revendications for a long time, but it wasn't until 1944 that the cause was heard. These claims have been particularly advocated by some women like the "Dames de Tivoli", Camille Fitte-Duval and Césaire Rosamond, who organized a conference on the subject in 1925. But there were also women like Irma Cécette⁶, Claude Carbet⁷ and Paulette Nardal who helped women win the right to vote.

3.7. Jenny Alpha (1910-2010)

Jenny Alpha was a Martinican woman who left her mark on the history of creole music. She was a singer and an actress and appeared in more than a hundred theatre productions and movies. In the post-war period, she was an activist for the recognition of Creole culture as part of the Négritude movement. She has made a major contribution to French culture.

⁵ In English: War cross 1939-1945. It's a French military decoration to honor people who fought with the Allies during World War II.

⁶ In Martinique, Irma Cécette is considered the first feminist. She was president of a mutual aid society and began to spread the idea of equality between men and women among the inhabitants of Saint-Pierre.

⁷ Claude Carbet, a Freemason and member of the "Émancipation Feminine" lodge, made her mark when she made a speech on March 31, 1931, in which she denounced all forms of inequality, defended homosexuals, women's right to control their own bodies, the right to vote...

4. City's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

Martinique and the different cities on this island don't really have practices in disseminating gender balanced history. The example mentioned above regarding the street in Fort-de-France that was renamed in the masculine form illustrates the inaction of the cities in Martinique. Indeed, the error has been pointed out several times and the request to correct the mistake had been made. However, the City Hall is not taking any action.

5. Local strategies

In Martinique, several historians and organizations are working with the aim of dissemination gender balanced history. For example, *L'Union des Femmes de Martinique* (UFM), the first feminist organization in the Caribbean, founded by Jane Léro. Initially, it was a local extension of the *Union des Femmes Françaises*, a movement initiated by women resistance fighters during the Second World War. Today, UFM's mission is to defend and promote women's rights to build a society of equality between women and men in Martinique. Among other things, UFM works to raise awareness about women in the history of Martinique and, more broadly, in the Caribbean and the world, because, as they explain, they are "convinced that history is essential for understanding ourselves, and even more so, the knowledge of women's history"⁸. To do this, they work on the valorization of a whole series of women, such as the "*charbonnières*" (charcoal workers) of Fort-de-France, or those who have carried various causes within social movements. UFM also offers several traveling exhibitions and workshops aimed at the general public. This very short, dynamic format is a first approach that raises awareness of social representations, misunderstood realities, clarifies certain concepts, etc. The association also offers training courses to help raise awareness and develop skills.

There is also *LimièKilti*, a cultural organization offering services combining history, culture and digital for public and/or private professionals. Mélody MOUTAMALLE, the founder, is currently working on an insertion project involving history, heritage, and art. She has also participated to the creation of tourist circuits, murals, and exhibitions. A chronological timeline of Martinique's history has also been created, and she would like to do the same but in the form of mini thematic timelines (on women's history, on the history of social movements, etc.).

⁸ Rita Bonheur. Témoignage : "Femmes, discriminations et violences : l'expérience militante de l'Union des Femmes de Martinique". Archipélices. Discriminations multiples et croisées, 6. hal-02045290, 2018

Culture Égalité (CE), is a feminist association based in Martinique which contributes to building a society based on gender equality, diversity, and solidarity. The association is aimed at all women, helping them to defend their rights and to be free, independent, and united. Among their objectives, there is the desire to make visible the heritage of women and their contribution to the social, political, economic, and cultural development of our society.

Other personalities, organizations and historians are also keen to help valorize women in history and promote gender equality.

6. Focus Groups with Young People: Analyses and results

It was difficult to find young people willing to take part in the focus group, so we created a questionnaire to gather as much information as possible on the subject.

6.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

First, we found that the participants' level of education and interest in history is very heterogeneous. Some have a high level of interest, others less or none. Their interest also depends on the period of history, with some periods being more interesting to them than others.

Also, the history of Martinique is rarely discussed at school, as the curriculum is not adapted to and focused on metropolitan France, on Europe. It is therefore more difficult to interest young people because they do not always feel involved.

This certainly explains why most of the young people didn't participate to workshops or activities with historical content. Some participates at conferences, at documentary screenings or at events that take place on March 8th but that's not the majority of them.

6.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The level of historical knowledges differs from one young person to another, depending on age, social background, personal interests, and studies. Their knowledge also depends on the subject, the period, etc. Furthermore, it has been noted that there is always more to learn, and that a same historical subject can be recounted differently depending on who reports and analyses it.

In any case, young people agree that the knowledge provided is not always enough. As mentioned above, one of the gaps they find is that not enough is said about Martinique's history. At school, the subjects covered are always the same, and some periods are seen

several times, sometimes even every year. It's also always the same countries, regions and people that are discussed. So, there's a huge lack of information on a whole part of the world's history. Even when they do learn about the country's history, there's a part of it that's missing, since the overseas regions are neglected. Most French people don't know the history of regions like Martinique, that's why it's clear that the knowledge provided is not enough.

This lack of knowledge also applies to gender issues since all the young people agree that they know many remarkable male figures in history, but very few women. Some of them know a few French women who have contributed to history like Marie Curie, Jeanne d'Arc, Simone Veil etc., but others very few. And at the local level, knowledge is more limited and it's noticeable that some young people are not familiar with any Martinican female figure.

We can therefore see that not all young people know the same number of remarkable women in history. Again, it depends on each person.

Most of the young people think that the representation of women in history is underestimated due to the patriarchal discourse of history. This can have a negative impact on the image that a girl or woman has of herself. However, they know that women hold a significant place in history. But the society is very patriarchal, and men focused and there is also a lack of political will in this area which explains the gender misrepresentation.

Some of the young people interviewed admit that they have never paid too much attention to the question of gender representation in history, but they still have the impression that they have heard more about men.

6.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

According to the young people, there are different ways to promote women's footprint in history. They mainly talk about non-formal education such as games, quizzes, exhibitions and interactive activities or workshops in which people are involved and participate. Everyone agrees that's important that people can feel integrated and be actor.

Another way to promote women's footprint in history is through culture for example books, movies, documentaries...for example the movie *Hidden Figures* highlights the actions of young black women and the differences that once existed. There are very few films like this one about women and they are not very known. Highlighting them and organizing screenings could raise awareness of women's contributions to history.

It's also possible to organize conferences, debates, podcasts, videos on the theme to spread portraits of women, tell their stories and raise awareness of female figures who have played an important role.

Using social networks such as YouTube, Facebook or Instagram can also help to promote women's footprint. Networks are used by everyone, and there are many features that can be used to make a publication attractive or playful enough to capture people's interest.

One of the young people gave the idea to organize a day dedicated to women in history. In general, female figures should be highlighted at cultural events but it would be easier if there were a day dedicated to these women.

School is the first place where young people encounter with history, but they are not taught (or very little) about the history of some territories and the role of women. Therefore, it would be necessary to change the history and geography curriculum to include women's stories by nuancing the exploits of men who were ultimately the work of a woman in the shadows, etc.

Finally, naming streets, airports, schools, etc. after women would also help to highlight and promote remarkable feminine figures.

7. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

Most of the stakeholders interested in the project and who could participate to the focus group are people who have studied or work in the field of history and/or gender. This explains why they have experience or a rather solid knowledge in the field of history. Some people who are not from this field were interested but were unable to take part in the focus group (for example, people from the prefecture or other associations).

Their expertise showed that women are poorly represented in history and their participation in shaping our societies is not documented. Madame Celma, for example, who works for the *Union des femmes Martinique* (UFM)⁹ began in the 1980s working on social movements. She realized that there were always women present, that some of them had played an important role, but that it was never highlighted. Today, work is being done to make these women better known, but they face challenges in term of content, in particular the lack of information and documentation. Therefore, working on the footprint of women in history requires an enormous amount of time. Whether it be in archives or elsewhere, there is very little information available compared to what can

⁹ The *Union des femmes de Martinique* (UFM) is a feminist association. The aim of this organization is to raise awareness of prevention issues relating to gender equality, violence against women, sexism, and discrimination

be found on men. Their experiences, struggles, and agency were often absent from official historical archives, which shows the little importance attributed to women in history.

Their experience with young people showed that most of them don't have enough information and knowledge in the field history. Content-wise, there is a lack and what young people need the most, is an intersectional perspective. History always addresses the white male point of view, and deliberately omits the "others' stories". Depending on their intersections (gender, origins, sexual orientation, class, etc.), people are more or less likely to be represented in the telling of the History.

However, they believe that some young people are interested in history so it would be possible to interest most of them and make them more aware of the history. Concerning the interest in women's history, they feel that it is growing, especially among young women, as they are seeking for identification and searching for heroines who resemble them. But to succeed in interesting as many people as possible, we need to succeed in generating that interest. For this purpose, there are several tools that could be used. It would be interesting, for example, to use storytelling or to ask them to represent one figure, by role-playing, miming, or drawing inspiration by what Adeline Rapon¹⁰ has done. It's important for young people to be actors themselves. It would also be interesting to use short documentaries, games, theater plays or gymkhana with QR codes, apps or board games where you can trace a "feminist timeline".

What the stakeholders see is that the contribution of women in history is rarely highlighted which also explains why young people and others have little knowledge or interest in the subject. In general, women in Martinique are forgotten on the national scale, but locally there are also concerns. However, many women in Martinique have contributed to history but their footprint in history is weak. Even if the participants can refer to the female footprint in history, most of them had to learn about the role of women in history outside their formal studies. They learned about it late and either by their entourage or through personal research. This shows the lack of women's footprint in history.

Good practices to promote gender balance in history would be to introduce women's participation every time we talk about history. It's important to highlight women and men's role and it's crucial to make every person aware of why it is important to promote gender balance in history.

¹⁰ Adeline Rapon is a French Afrofeminist photographer, visual artist, author and influencer born in Paris in 1990. During the first COVID 19 pandemic-related lockdown in 2020, she created a series of self-portraits entitled *Fanm Fô* ("strong woman" in Creole), in which she stages herself by reproducing certain poses from photographs of black Caribbean women. The aim was to highlight these women but also to questioning the clichés these portraits conveyed.

Nonformal education activities (games, leisure activities, sports, etc) could also be a good way to promote gender equality.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, we can assert that gender inequality is still present in Martinique, and it is also manifested through history. This explains why the contributions of women are rarely, if ever, highlighted. However, efforts are being made, and many individuals and organizations are actively working to raise awareness and bring recognition to the women who have contributed to the history of our society.

Despite these efforts, women from Martinique still face significant challenges related to gender inequality. In many sectors, they still have to fight for equal recognition and access to the same opportunities as men. Gender stereotypes persist, influencing social perceptions and expectations regarding the role of women in society.

It is therefore crucial to continue initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality in Martinique. This includes awareness campaigns, educational programs, and public policies that promote equal opportunities. By valuing the contributions of women and fully integrating them into the historical narrative, we can not only do justice to their heritage by correcting historical biases but also inspire future generations to work towards a more equitable society.

In sum, although progress has been made, the path towards gender equality in Martinique requires constant vigilance and commitment. Recognizing and celebrating the achievements of women in our collective past is an essential step towards achieving true equality and building a more inclusive society that respects the rights of everyone.

In this context, the HerStory initiative in Martinique is a determining tool for recognizing these women who have made history but have often remained in the shadows. It is therefore essential to bring them into the light they deserve.